

ISic1454

I.Sicily inscription 1454

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Necropolis of Manicalunga

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8750

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Σιλανός
2. Εύθυμίδα

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284893

EDR 112420

EDCS 41300077

EDCS 64800245

PHI 175691

Bibliography

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